

**Project SOP D-JRP17-
WP1.SOP2 – Epidemiological
questionnaire
Workpackage 1**

Responsible Partner: INIAV

Contributing partners: ANSES, APHA, BfR,
FLI, IZSAM, NDRVMI, INSA, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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Project Acronym	IDEMBRU
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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EMA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL QUESTIONNAIRE

Date of sampling: ____/____/____

1. Country / Region: _____

2. Sampling area/ total area: _____

3. Geographic coordinates: Latitude: _____ Longitude: _____

4. Type of Biotope and animal group the collection is done:

Forest	Freshwater habitats	Coastal Regions
Canidae	Amphibians	Marine Mammals
Rodents	Fish	Fish / Reptiles
Ruminants	Aquatic rodents	Crustaceans
Wildboars	Water	Filter feeders
Soil		

5. Is it multispecies or single species place:

____ No

____ Yes. Which other species: _____

6. Collected samples:

Species / Environment	Type of samples	Number

7. Animals access to surrounding areas:

- Forest
- River/Stream

- Lake
- Swamp
- Pastures for other type of animals
- Urban area
- other: _____

8. Animals access to surrounding areas:

- Community controlled sources
- See

- Well
- River/Stream
- Lake
- Rainwater collection spot

Owner/ manager/care taker/..... has been informed that
sample collection and data collected in this questionnaire will serve OHEJP IDEMBRU project only.